

AI Techniques Aid for Predicting the Collection Demands of Industrial Plastic Waste From Multiple Facilities

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Abstract

A clear understanding of plastic waste collection potential in a locality is key to optimize the recycling system in terms of collection and disposal schedules, vehicle deployment, and personnel arrangements. This study aims to fill this gap by predicting individual collection demands of industrial plastic waste (IPW) using an artificial intelligence technique, demonstrated for multiple types of facilities in Fukuoka Prefecture, Japan.

We developed a machine learning approach to predict the amount of IPW to be collected from individual facilities based on daily waste manifest data. Through the explorations from multiple aspects, the best models were selected and high prediction accuracies were achieved for 5 types of facilities: supermarket (84.6%), hospital (84.4%), logistics company (78.2%), food manufacturing company (82.5%), and building management company (81.1%). The root mean square error performed not so effectively in selecting the optimal prediction model. The IPW collection from hospital was the easiest to predict accurately. Climate conditions were not useful for the hospital and logistics company but others. Moreover, we identified the robust prediction periods for these facilities from September 1, 2020: supermarket (20 days), hospital (2 days), logistics company (6 days), food manufacturing company (1 day), and building management company (2 days).

Key Words: AI technology, collection demand, future prediction, industrial plastic waste, waste manifest

1. Introduction

Understanding industrial plastic waste (IPW) collection potential clearly in a locality is key to optimize the recycling system in terms of collection and disposal schedules, vehicle deployment, and personnel arrangements. However, the prediction accuracy depends on the prediction period and target facilities. Thus, local recycling companies should determine (1) a suitable period to make accurate predictions and (2) for which type of facilities it is easier to predict IPW. To answer these questions, prediction tests over

a long period and for multiple types of facilities are needed.

Various statistical models, such as multiple linear regression models^{1, 2)}, vector autoregression³⁾, and seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average^{4, 5)} have been applied in previous studies for prediction problems in waste generation. In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) techniques for analyzing “big data” have increasingly been utilized for such problems owing to their higher prediction accuracy in many fields^{6–8)}.

To support waste management, an improved sup-

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port vector machine (SVM) model was developed to forecast the weekly generation of municipal solid waste (MSW) in the city of Mashhad, Iran⁹). To optimize the cost of waste collection and transportation, an artificial neural network (ANN)–genetic algorithm model was combined with the response surface method to predict MSW generation in Langkawi Island, Malaysia¹⁰). ANN and decision tree algorithms were applied to predict MSW in Ontario, Canada, using socio-economic and demographic parameters¹¹). In Japan, Cong *et al.* applied 28 models to predict daily IPW collection demands from a supermarket in Fukuoka and validated the accuracy of the selected model for seven days¹²). However, the predictions for different types of facilities to determine (1) in which facilities IPW is easier to predict and (2) the robust prediction periods were not compared in these studies.

In this context, the aim of this study is to answer the following questions: 1) How do we improve the prediction accuracy of daily IPW collection from five types of facilities using a machine learning approach? 2) Is the root mean square error (RMSE) effective in selecting the optimal prediction models? 3) Are the climate conditions and prior processes essential for each type of facility in future predictions? 4) What type of facility is easier to predict IPW? 5) How long is the robust prediction period for these facilities?

2. Methods

2.1 Data and workflow

The IPW collection amounts were obtained from waste manifest data of a local recycling company in Fukuoka Prefecture. The raw manifest data contained individual records on the daily amount collected (kg), collection date (from April 1, 2018, to September 30, 2020), facility name, intermediate treatment facilities (destinations of collections), and the name of the collector for each collection. In addition, this study included climate data from the daily weather report¹³) because it may impact IPW collections. As shown in Table 1, this study focuses on five types of facilities: supermarket, hospital, logistics company, food manufacturing company, and building management company.

Fig. 1 shows the workflow applied in developing an ML approach for the prediction of the daily col-

lection demands from individual facilities. Data on IPW collections from five facilities were used as ML targets. First, we combined the daily records of the IPW collection amounts with daily weather data. The data in the fitting period were fitted to all 28 models that were stored in a regression learner application from Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox (v.12.1) in MATLAB R2021a. Then, new predictions were made using all fit models in the validation period. Subsequently, the accuracies of the predictions were evaluated to select the best candidate models. Finally, we evaluated the accuracy of predictions with the candidate best models after excluding the climatic variable for each facility to verify its importance. Based on the final results, the robust prediction period and the best model were determined for each facility.

2.2 Data preparation and model fitting

The raw manifest data until August 30, 2020, were extracted for fitting, and the remaining data in September 2020 were used for validation. Details on data processing and model fitting can be found in Cong *et al.*¹²). In contrast, we adjusted the scope of conditions for the climate impact variables in data preparation to make it reasonable for different types of facilities, as shown in Table 2. Moreover, we declined the variable selection process to choose the best model by comparing the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE)¹⁴) of all validated results rather than selecting it by referring to the RMSE¹⁵) in the model fitting process. Since industrial waste generations may contain many outliers, the optimal prediction model which can deal with such data needs to be selected through multiple models. The RMSE indicator was reported to be not enough for comparing performances of models¹⁶). Thus, such model fitting process was determined including more prior processes and indicators for better accuracy.

2.3 Case setting for validation

To verify the effectiveness of prior processes (data smoothing and outlier embedding) and category conversion (for the weekday variable), four different cases were set for model validation, as shown in Fig. 1. For outlier embedding, a 3-Sigma method (mean $\pm 3 \times$ standard deviation) was used to detect the outliers for the variables corresponding to the collection amounts in training data, and linear interpolation was used as a cleaning method to fill the outliers.

Table 1 Details on daily collection amounts of IPW for five types of facilities from April 2018 to September 2020

Facility type	Category				Number of collection records
	Daily collection amount-kg				
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation	
Supermarket	10	50	19.4	6.3	912
Hospital	10	60	28.3	9.5	910
Logistics company	40	520	225.8	86.2	909
Food manufacture company	70	1,120	593.1	153.5	912
Building management company	10	200	92.2	23.8	899

Table 2 Description of the independent variables used in this study

Variable	Description
Day_num	day number from 2018.4.1 to 2020.9.30
Weekday	what day it was the day
Pre_d_climate	category type on climate impact of previous day: wind speed $\geq 10 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, daily rainfall $\geq 20 \text{ mm}$, highest temperature ≥ 35 degree
Pre_d_holiday	category type on previous day belongs to holiday or not
Interval	the interval between the present and former collection day
Num_fday	the amount on former collection day
Num_sday_fw	the amount on the same day of the former week

Fig. 1 Workflow used to predict the industrial plastic waste (IPW) collection amount from the collection facilities in Fukuoka using machine learning

Then, a moving-mean method and a smoothing factor of 0.25 (default value) were used in the cleaned data for data smoothing. Through comparisons, the candidate best models for the four cases were selected. Similar predictions were made by using the data without the climate impact variable. Finally, the best

models with the lowest MAPE for each facility and the robust prediction period were determined. The robust period is defined as the number of days from the first validation day (September 1, 2020) to the day when the mean accuracies were higher than the monthly mean accuracies in September 2020.

Table 3 Performances on the predictions of IPW collection amounts from a supermarket in September 2020

Indicator	Model with the lowest RMSE				Best model	
	Baseline cases		Processed cases		With CI	Without CI
	Normal	Optimized	Normal	Optimized		
RMSE	5.9842	5.9989	3.6885	3.7289	6.2467	6.2497
R ²	0.11	0.11	0.34	0.32	0.02	0.01
Model used	Bagged trees	Optimal ensemble	Bagged trees	Optimal GPR	Coarse Gaussian SVM	Coarse Gaussian SVM
CC	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
D&O	no	no	yes	yes	no	no
MAPE	19.7%	23.9%	16.4%	17.5%	15.4%	15.6%
MA	80.3%	76.1%	83.6%	82.5%	84.6%	84.4%

Note: CC means category conversion; D&O means data smoothing and outlier embedding; MA means mean accuracy; Baseline cases mean the predictions using the data without category conversion and prior processes; processed cases are the predictions using data after category conversion and prior processes; Normal means the prediction is made by the model with the lowest RMSE in the unoptimized model group; Optimized means the prediction is made by the model with the lowest RMSE in the optimized model group; CI means climate impact.

Fig. 2 Predicted and observed values on daily IPW collection amount (kg) from a supermarket in September 2020 (no collection was recorded on 7th day)

3. Results and discussion

As mentioned above, 28 models were fitted by the data until August 30, 2020 and then used to predict the daily collection amounts from five types of facilities for September 2020. The results are discussed for each type of facility as follows.

Supermarket:

By evaluating the results of all models, the best model for the supermarket was the coarse Gaussian SVM model (monthly mean accuracy: 84.6% in Table 3). As shown in Table 3, the best model with the highest mean accuracy was detected with the lowest MAPE, rather than from the models with the lowest RMSE (in four cases). This implies that the RMSE in-

dicator does not select the best model for this facility. Comparing the two normal cases, we found that the accuracy of the processed case was improved, which indicated the usefulness of category conversion and prior processes for the bagged trees model. After verifying the indicators of the best model, we conclude that the optimized model and prior processes do not improve the prediction accuracy. However, category conversion was helpful. The climate impact variable was effective in the predictions, showing that the predictions for the supermarket were easily affected by climate conditions.

As shown in Fig. 2, the values predicted by the best model (orange lines) appeared to be smoother than the observed values (blue lines). The robust

Table 4 Performances on the predictions for a hospital

Indicator	Model with the lowest RMSE				Best model	
	Baseline cases		Processed cases		With CI	Without CI
	Normal	Optimized	Normal	Optimized		
RMSE	7.1575	7.1265	2.9377	2.9624	7.6406	7.5982
R ²	0.43	0.44	0.83	0.82	0.36	0.36
Model used	Bagged trees	Optimal ensemble	Exponential	Optimal GPR	Rational quadratic	Rational quadratic
CC	no	no	yes	yes	no	no
D&O	no	no	yes	yes	no	no
MAPE	16.0%	17.6%	20.9%	18.1%	15.8%	15.6%
MA	84.0%	82.4%	79.1%	81.9%	84.2%	84.4%

Fig. 3 Predicted and observed values on daily IPW collection amount (kg) from a hospital in September 2020 (no collection on 7th day)

prediction period was confirmed as the first 20 days (mean accuracy: 87.8%) from September 1, 2020. Therefore, the predictions lasting to any day of this period would ensure that their mean accuracy is better than the monthly mean value. On the other hand, those days with extremely low prediction accuracies showed that the prediction accuracy dropped on some days. The trend learned by the model made the predicted values slightly vary around 20 kg so that significant errors would occur once the observed values were far from 20. In other words, the amount of 10 kg in training data occurred out of order (e.g., an observed interval for a period without the occurrence of 10 was up to 57 days), resulting in the fitted model lacking accuracy in predicting this value (i.e., collections on 15th, 18th, 22nd, 25th). It implies that some effective variables should be introduced to this data for better learning the occurrence pattern of 10 kg.

Hospital:

According to our results, the best model for this hospital was the rational quadratic model (monthly mean accuracy: 84.4%, Table 4). As shown in Table 4, the best model with the lowest mean accuracy was detected from all predictions, not from the models with the lowest RMSE. Therefore, the RMSE indicator does not select the best model for this facility. We found that the category conversion and prior processes did not improve the prediction accuracy by the best model. Moreover, the climate impact was found to have a negative impact on the prediction accuracy. This implies that IPW predictions for hospitals are not easily affected by climatic conditions.

As shown in Fig. 3, the values predicted by the best model appeared to be more stable than the observed values. The prediction accuracy for the days with collection records of approximately 30 kg was significantly better than that of days with collection records of approximately 40 kg. We found that the

Table 5 Performances on the predictions for a logistics company

Indicator	Model with the lowest RMSE				Best model	
	Baseline cases		Processed cases		With CI	Without CI
	Normal	Optimized	Normal	Optimized		
RMSE	43.119	41.811	14.094	14.139	18.447	18.425
R ²	0.75	0.77	0.97	0.97	0.94	0.94
Model used	Bagged trees	Optimal ensemble	Rational quadratic	Optimal GPR	Fine tree	Fine tree
CC	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
D&O	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
MAPE	49.1%	38.8%	34.0%	37.1%	24.5%	21.8%
MA	50.9%	61.2%	66.0%	62.9%	75.5%	78.2%

Fig. 4 Predicted and observed daily IPW collection amounts (kg) from a logistics company in September 2020 (no collection on 7th day)

robust prediction period was the first two days (mean accuracy: 88.7%) from September 1, 2020. This implies that the model with these data is not suitable for long-term applications.

Logistics company:

According to our results, the best model for this logistics company was the fine tree model (monthly mean accuracy: 78.2%, Table 5). As shown in Table 5, the best model with the highest mean accuracy was not detected in the models with the lowest RMSE (in four cases). This implies that the RMSE indicator does not select the best model for this facility. We found that category conversion and prior processes helped to improve the prediction accuracy by the best model. Moreover, the climate impact was found to have a negative impact on the prediction accuracy. It also reflects that IPW predictions from logistics companies are not easily affected by climatic conditions.

As shown in Fig. 4, the values predicted by the best model (orange lines) appeared to be smoother than the observed values (blue lines). The prediction accuracy for the days with collection records of approximately 200 kg was significantly better than that of the other days. We found that the robust prediction period was the first six days (mean accuracy: 78.4%) from September 1, 2020.

Food manufacturing company:

As shown in Table 6, the best model for this food manufacturing company was the bagged trees model (monthly mean accuracy: 82.5%). The best model with the highest mean accuracy was the same as that of the model with the lowest RMSE. Hence, the RMSE indicator selects the best model for this facility. Comparing the two normal cases, we found that the accuracy of the processed case dropped, which meant the ineffectiveness of category conversion and prior processes for this model. Compared to the

Table 6 Performances on the predictions for a food manufacturing company

Indicator	Model with the lowest RMSE				Best model	
	Baseline cases		Processed cases		With CI	Without CI
	Normal	Optimized	Normal	Optimized		
RMSE	130.96	129.38	129.22	124.33	130.96	131.5
R ²	0.27	0.28	0.29	0.33	0.27	0.27
Model used	Bagged trees	Optimal GPR	Bagged trees	Optimal GPR	Bagged trees	Bagged trees
CC	no	no	yes	yes	no	no
D&O	no	no	yes	yes	no	no
MAPE	17.5%	23.8%	19.1%	20.3%	17.5%	18.7%
MA	82.5%	76.2%	80.9%	79.7%	82.5%	81.3%

Fig. 5 Predicted and observed daily IPW collection amounts (kg) from a food manufacturing company in September 2020 (no collection on 7th day)

result of the supermarket, category conversion and prior processes by the same model could affect the prediction accuracy in different directions. We can conclude that the optimized model, category conversion, and prior processes do not improve the prediction accuracy by this best model. However, the climate impact variable improved prediction accuracy. Therefore, IPW predictions for food manufacturing companies are easily affected by climate conditions.

As shown in Fig. 5, the values predicted by the best model (orange lines) appeared to be more stable than the observed values (blue lines). The prediction accuracy for the days with collection records of approximately 600 kg was significantly better than that of the other days. We found that the robust prediction period was the first day (accuracy: 90.4%) from September 1, 2020. This implies that the model with these data is not suitable for long-term applications.

Building management company:

As shown in Table 7, the best model for this build-

ing management company was the quadratic SVM model (monthly mean accuracy: 81.1%). The best model with the highest mean accuracy had the lowest MAPE rather than the lowest RMSE (in four cases). Thus, the RMSE indicator does not select the best model for this facility. After verifying the indicators of the best model, we found that the optimized model and prior processes did not improve the prediction accuracy. On the other hand, category conversion was helpful. The climate impact variable was effective for predictions. Therefore, the IPW predictions for building management companies are easily affected by climate conditions.

As shown in Fig. 6, the values predicted by the best model (orange lines) appeared to fit well for the days with peak records (blue lines) but not for the others. We found that the robust prediction period was the first two days (accuracy: 86.7%) from September 1, 2020. Hence, the model with these data is not suitable for long-term applications.

Table 7 Performances of four cases from the predictions for a building management company

Indicator	Model with the lowest RMSE				Best model	
	Baseline cases		Processed cases		With CI	Without CI
	Normal	Optimized	Normal	Optimized		
RMSE	14.337	14.73	5.2381	5.1929	17.563	17.073
R ²	0.62	0.6	0.92	0.92	0.44	0.47
Model used	Bagged trees	Optimal ensemble	Robust linear	Optimal ensemble	Quadratic SVM	Quadratic SVM
CC	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
D&O	no	no	yes	yes	no	no
MAPE	35.2%	35.4%	29.4%	36.8%	18.9%	24.4%
MA	64.8%	64.6%	70.6%	63.2%	81.1%	75.6%

Fig. 6 Predicted and observed values on daily IPW collection amount (kg) from a building management company in September 2020 (no collection on 7th day)

From the above comparisons, we can conclude that the IPW collection amounts from the hospital are the easiest to predict (no need for prior processing, category conversion, and climate impact variable). Another major reason may be that there are least gradients in its collection amounts, making it easier to learn the patterns of occurrence for predictions. Fig. 7 shows the daily prediction accuracies of IPW collection amounts by five facilities in September 2020. The prediction accuracies for these facilities are accurate enough (e.g., monthly mean: around 80% and daily mean on 1st: higher than 90%) for making optimal collection schedules or vehicle/personnel arrangements for the next day even longer-term. Although the monthly mean prediction accuracy of IPW collection amounts from the supermarket is the highest, there are significantly large errors for some days, e.g., 15th, 18th, 22nd, and 25th. In contrast, the monthly mean prediction accuracy for the logistics company was the lowest, but the accuracy

of each prediction was higher than 60%. Hence, these models can predict the collection demands with high individual prediction accuracies (up to 100%); however, their performances would drop after the prediction period. Therefore, determining the robust prediction period is essential for solving real problems by using the AI technique. More challenges on the model performances could be made by validating with randomly sampled test data and introducing more metrics in evaluations e.g., bias, precision, and extremes¹⁶.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we developed an AI-based approach to predict IPW collection demands for five types of facilities based on daily waste manifest data in Fukuoka Prefecture. The answers to the questions mentioned in the introduction section are listed as follows:

1. Through the explorations from prior processes, category conversion, optimization, and variable

Fig. 7 Prediction accuracies on daily collection amounts of IPW in September 2020 for five facilities (mean accuracies in brackets) in Fukuoka (no collection was recorded on September 7)

selection on climate impact, we searched the best models and achieved high monthly mean accuracies by them: supermarket (84.6%), hospital (84.4%), logistics company (78.2%), food manufacturing company (82.5%), and building management company (81.1%). Although the monthly mean prediction accuracy of IPW collection amounts from the supermarket was the highest, there were extremely large errors for some days. In contrast, the monthly mean prediction accuracy for the logistics company was the lowest, but the accuracy of each prediction was higher than 60%.

2. The indicator of RMSE was demonstrated to be not so effective as the MAPE in selecting the optimal prediction model.
3. Climate conditions were important for the predictions of IPW collection demands from supermarkets, food manufacturing, and building management companies. However, they were not useful for hospitals and logistics companies. We found that prior processes were not always helpful for improving the prediction accuracies and should be explored on a case-by-case basis.
4. The IPW collection amounts from the hospital were the easiest to predict due to no need for prior processing, category conversion, and climate im-

pact variable.

5. These models predicted the collection demands with high individual prediction accuracies (up to 100%); however, their performances would drop after the prediction period. Hence, determining the robust prediction period is essential for solving real problems by using the AI technique. We detected the robust prediction period for five facilities from September 1, 2020: supermarket (20 days), hospital (2 days), logistics company (6 days), food manufacturing company (1 d), and building management company (2 days).

In the next step, future applications using these predicted collection demands will be explored, *e.g.*, capacitated vehicle routing problems, optimal collection schedule problems, and vehicle/personnel arrangements for cost optimization. Once the daily records of customer numbers, sales amount, and production amount are available, the detailed factors for better prediction accuracy will be clarified.

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References

- 1) Lebreton L. and A. Andrady (2019) Future scenarios of global plastic waste generation and disposal. *Palgrave Communications*, 5(1), 6.
- 2) Isobe A., S. Iwasaki, K. Uchida and T. Tokai (2019) Abundance of non-conservative microplastics in the upper ocean from 1957 to 2066. *Nature Communications*, 10(1), 417.
- 3) Gardiner R. and P. Hajek (2020) Municipal waste generation, R&D intensity, and economic growth nexus—A case of EU regions. *Waste Management*, 114, 124–135.
- 4) Navarro-Esbri J., E. Diamadopoulos and D. Ginestar (2002) Time series analysis and forecasting techniques for municipal solid waste management. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 35(3), 201–214.
- 5) Ceylan Z., S. Bulkan and S. Eevli (2020) Prediction of medical waste generation using SVR, GM (1, 1) and ARIMA models: A case study for megacity Istanbul. *Journal of Environmental Health Science & Engineering*, 18(2), 687–697.
- 6) Hatton C.M., L.W. Paton, D. McMillan, J. Cusens, S. Gilbody and P.A. Tiffin (2019) Predicting persistent depressive symptoms in older adults: A machine learning approach to personalised mental healthcare. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 246, 857–860.
- 7) Alizamir M., O. Kisi, A.N. Ahmed, C. Mert, C.M. Fai, S. Kim, N.W. Kim and A. El-Shafie (2020) Advanced machine learning model for better prediction accuracy of soil temperature at different depths. *PLoS One*, 15(4), e0231055.
- 8) Oliveira V., V. Sousa and C. Dias-Ferreira (2019) Artificial neural network modelling of the amount of separately-collected household packaging waste. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 210, 401–409.
- 9) Noori R., M.A. Abdoli, A.A. Ghasrodashti and M. Jalili Ghazizade (2009) Prediction of municipal solid waste generation with combination of support vector machine and principal component analysis: A case study of mashhad. *Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy*, 28(2), 249–258.
- 10) Shamshiry E., M. Mokhtar, A.M. Abdulai, I. Komoo and N. Yahaya (2014) Combining artificial neural network-genetic algorithm and response surface method to predict waste generation and optimize cost of solid waste collection and transportation process in Langkawi Island, Malaysia. *Malaysian Journal of Science. Series B, Physical & Earth Sciences*, 33(2), 118–140.
- 11) Kannangara M., R. Dua, L. Ahmadi and F. Bensebaa (2018) Modeling and prediction of regional municipal solid waste generation and diversion in canada using machine learning approaches. *Waste Management*, 74, 3–15.
- 12) Cong R., A. Fujiyama and T. Matsumoto (2022) Collection of industrial plastic waste during the COVID-19 pandemic: A case study of the wholesale and retail trade sector in Fukuoka prefecture, Japan. *Journal of Human and Environmental Symbiosis*, 38(1), 46–55.
- 13) Japan Meteorological Agency, Download the Climate Data in the Past of Fukuoka Prefecture, <http://www.data.jma.go.jp/gmd/risk/obsdl/index.php>, (accessed 2021-10-31).
- 14) de Myttenaere A., B. Golden, B. Le Grand and F. Rossi (2016) Mean absolute percentage error for regression models. *Neurocomputing*, 192, 38–48.
- 15) Chai T. and R.R. Draxler (2014) Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) or Mean Absolute Error (MAE)? — Arguments against avoiding RMSE in the literature. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 7(3), 1247–1250.
- 16) Liemohn M.W., A.D. Shane, A.R. Azari, A.K. Petersen, B.M. Swiger and A. Mukhopadhyay (2021) RMSE is not enough: Guidelines to robust data-model comparisons for magnetospheric physics. *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, 218, 105624.

AI技術による産業系廃プラスチックの回収需要量の予測 —複数施設を対象に—

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摘 要

廃プラスチックの回収ポテンシャルを把握することは、リサイクルシステムの最適化のために重要である。特に回収処理スケジュールの作成、配車、人員配置等を行う上では、必要な情報である。本研究の目的は、福岡県において複数施設より回収される産業系廃プラスチックの回収需要量の将来予測を行うことである。

本研究では、産業廃棄物管理票（マニフェスト）を活用した、個別施設から排出される廃プラの1日あたり回収需要量予測のための機械学習手法を開発した。複数の調整実験により最適なモデルを検出し、次に示す高い予測精度を得た：スーパー（84.6%）、病院（84.4%）、物流企業（78.2%）、食品工場（82.5%）、ビル管理企業（81.1%）。一方、平均平方二乗誤差が最適な予測モデルの検出には有効ではなかった。廃プラ回収需要量に関して病院施設が一番予測しやすいことを明らかにした。気候条件が、病院と物流企業の将来予測には寄与しないことを解明した。さらに、2020年9月1日時点における、有効な予測期間はスーパー（20日間）、病院（2日間）、物流企業（6日間）、食品工場（1日間）、ビル管理企業（2日間）であると検出された。

キーワード：AI技術、回収需要、将来予測、産業系廃プラスチック、産業廃棄物管理票（マニフェスト）